

A PARALLEL APPROACH IN UNDERSTANDING *XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA*: THE COSTA RICA CONTRIBUTION

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Xylella fastidiosa is endemic in Costa Rica. The bacterium was originally detected in the 1980's in coffee plants causing a milder version of coffee leaf scorch named "crespera". Consequently, in the last decade, *X. fastidiosa* has been detected and isolated from more than 20 different economic important crops and ornamentals, and most importantly extending the geographic range of detection of the bacteria. However, although the bacterium has great potential for disease and it is widespread throughout the country, the symptoms related to infected plants are usually mild or asymptomatic. In 2015, the European Union closed the importation of ornamentals from Costa Rica, alleging that *X. fastidiosa* was introduced in this matter into Europe and that is related to the serious epidemic disease affecting Olives. It is known that *X. fastidiosa* strains isolated from Costa Rica represent a broader genetic variability than in other countries. The report of ST53 *X. fastidiosa* strains from Costa Rica is of particular interest. In this direction, our contribution is based on isolating *X. fastidiosa* from different hosts to allow a broader genomic characterization and comparison with the European strains. Complementary to genetic profiling, we are focused in phenotypic characterization of *X. fastidiosa* strains, through the standardization of bacteriological, biological and immunological based assays that could eventually be used in reference and research units for *X. fastidiosa* profiling.